

THE INFLUENCE OF HEAT-TREATMENT ON THE DRY SLIDING WEAR BEHAVIOUR OF SAFFIL-REINFORCED AA6061 COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The steady-state wear of elemental aluminium alloy AA6061 and AA6061 based Saffil fibre-reinforced composites, manufactured by a PM route, was investigated with a pin-on-disc configuration under dry sliding conditions. For both the monolithic alloy and the MMC, a better dry sliding wear resistance was found in the peak-aged condition than after over-ageing, except for the lowest load, where the alloy shows an insignificant difference. Scanning electron microscopy suggested that the controlling wear mechanism for all the specimens was load dependent. With the improvement in the flow stress of the alloy matrix, the wear resistance of the MMC was found to be better in the peak-aged than the over-aged condition, as the tendency for the fracture of Saffil fibres was reduced and resulted in a decrease in the delamination rate.

KEYWORDS: dry sliding wear, heat-treatment, Saffil fibre, aluminium alloy, metal-matrix composites, pin-on-disc.

INTRODUCTION

Aluminium alloy based metal matrix composites have been commercialised by Toyota Motor Company in making the ring land of diesel engine pistons [1]. Following this application, many studies reported an improvement in the lubricated sliding wear resistance by incorporating the ceramic reinforcement into the aluminium alloys, regardless of the test methods used [2]. However, in a dry sliding condition, the wear resistance of the composite was complicated. Although several studies reported that the enhancement of wear resistance was achieved by the incorporation of ceramics [3-4], others suggested that this phenomenon was not always the case, as the benefit of the ceramic reinforcement was found to be load dependent [2,5]. For example, while the composite showed a substantial improvement in wear performance at low loads, a comparable or even inferior wear resistance was shown by the composite, compared to the monolithic alloy, as the applied load was sufficiently high to cause the fracture of the reinforcements.

In view of the many applications which require a heat-treatment to optimise the mechanical properties, the influence of the heat-treatment on the wear resistance has also received attention. The literature contains several references to lubricated sliding and abrasive wear resistance of 2000 series aluminium-SiC metal-matrix composites (MMCs) which showed improved wear resistance when tested in the over-aged compared to the peak-aged condition. The improvement was found to be due to the ageing effects on the interface bonding between

the reinforcement and the matrix [6-8]. For example, Pan and Cheng [6] found that the over-aged 20 vol% SiC reinforced 2124 Al based composite had a better lubricated sliding wear resistance than that in peak-aged condition, which was considered to be due to the change of the fracture path associated with the precipitation of intermetallics. This in turn reduced the extent of pull-out of the SiC particles and caused less damage to both the pin and the disc by third body wear processes. Wang and Rack [7], and Lin and Liu [8] also reported a similar improvement in abrasive wear performance in an over-aged condition.

While AA2014-SiC and AA6061-SiC MMCs have been studied extensively, far less attention has been given to AA6061- Al_2O_3 fibre (Saffil) MMCs. Previous work showed that the enhancement of the wear performance of the composites was load dependent. In the present study, three different loads were used to investigate the influence of heat-treatment on the steady-state dry sliding wear resistance of an AA6061 elemental alloy and a Saffil-reinforced AA6061 composite.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Materials

The materials used in this research were an AA6061 elemental alloy (1.1%Mg, 0.76%Si, 0.30%Cu, 0.20%Cr, 0.32%Fe, 0.02%Zn) and 20vol.% δ -alumina(Al_2O_3) fibres (also known as Saffil) reinforced AA6061 elemental alloy based composite, which were produced by a powder metallurgy route from the elemental powders. The as-extruded elemental alloys and composites were machined into a pin of length 20mm with a flat surface of 6mm in diameter at both ends, in the direction parallel to the extrusion axis, so that the Saffil fibres were normal to the flat surface. Before testing, the samples were given a T6 heat-treatment, of $530\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hours, iced water quenched and then artificially aged at 160°C for a period of time before quenching in ice water. Ageing periods of 16 hours and 10 hours were given to the monolithic alloy and the composites respectively, to achieve the peak-aged (PA) condition [9]. To produce the over-aged (OA) condition, the materials were aged at 260°C for 24 hours following the same solution treatment and quenching as above. The Vickers hardness of the as-extruded (AEx) and heat-treated specimens is given in Table 1. Each value is an average of 6 indentations made with a load of 20kg.

Table 1: Vickers hardness and the density of the materials

Volume Fraction, %	Hardness, HV20			Calculated Density, g/cm^3
	As-extruded	Peak-aged	Over-aged	
0	47	122	56	2.70
20	60	118	63	2.82

EN24 discs (1.40%Ni, 1.17%Cr, 0.63%Mn, 0.38%C, 0.29%Si, 0.25%Mo, bal. Fe) were used as the counterfaces. They were heat-treated to the hardness of 560HV30, in a manner similar to that used by Gurcan and Baker [10].

Experimental Procedure

The pin-on-disc configuration was used for the unlubricated sliding wear testing at room temperature in air under dry conditions, with the pin mounted vertically on the tester arm at one end and the other pin surface held against the rotating EN24 disc. The AA6061 alloys and composites were used as the pin, and the EN24 disc was used as the counterface. All the tests were performed under a constant sliding velocity of 0.19m/s at loads of 1.1N, 9.8N and 48.3N. The friction force was recorded during the tests via a load cell, which consisted of four strain gauges (full-bridge).

Prior to the test, the flat surface of the pin was lightly finished by sliding against 600 grit SiC paper which was adhered to the disc specimen, while the pin was mounted on the tester arm. The EN24 disc specimens were ground to a constant roughness of about $0.70\mu\text{m}$ Ra, and measured using a Talysurf 5-120 surface profilometer.

The wear of the pins was recorded by measuring the weight loss of the pins using a micro balance of accuracy 10^{-5} g. Except for the load of 1.1N, where the process was interrupted every 300m, to enable a measurable weight loss to be recorded, each measurement was made by interrupting the test every 100m of sliding distance. The weight loss recorded was converted to a volume loss by dividing by the calculated density of the material [11]. All the specimens followed a single track of 50mm in diameter and the EN24 disc was changed for each surface of the pin tested. Before each measurement, the pin was cleaned ultrasonically while immersed in methanol and then blown dry in air. The disc was cleaned by the same method as the pin although no measurement of weight change was made. Two readings were made for each weighing of the pin and the mean taken.

The microscopic examination of the monolithic alloy and the composites was undertaken by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). An EDAX facility, which was incorporated into the SEM, was used to provide chemical compositions from the worn surfaces.

RESULTS

Under dry sliding conditions, it is found by experiment that a running-in period is sometimes observed before a steady-state wear rate was achieved [12]. In the present study, although the steady-state wear behaviour is the main interest, it is worth noting that as the applied load increased to 48.3N, the metallic debris generated during the first few meters of running-in accumulated at the leading edge of the pin due to the repeated sliding along the same track. A greater extent of accumulation was consistently found on the monolithic alloy than the composite, regardless of the conditions of heat-treatment. As the accumulated debris were weakly attached at the leading edge of the pin specimen and might suddenly detach as sliding action proceeded, the debris was removed by a light pressure, after the first 100m of sliding distance was completed. Fig. 1 shows the accumulated debris which was removed from the leading edge of the pin. As a result of this removal, the wear rate of the monolithic alloy for the first 100m of sliding distance was found to be up to eight times greater than that of the composite. If the accumulated debris is not removed and its weight is taken into account when the pin is weighed, then less wear may be recorded for the monolithic alloy than the composite. Therefore, if the wear results produced within a short sliding distance are taken as normal, without having distinguished the running-in period from the steady-state wear process, the benefit of Saffil reinforcement in improving the wear resistance of the aluminium

alloy would have been misleading. In the present experiments, some evidence of extruded material at the trailing edge [2] was found in both the monolithic alloy and the composite and the extent increased with the applied load.

Fig. 1: SEM micrograph shows the accumulated debris which was removed from the leading edge of the monolithic alloy.

By plotting the volume loss versus sliding distance, the running-in period was identified and the relationship between the steady-state wear and the sliding distance was then plotted by normalising with the running-in wear rate, as in Fig. 2. For all cases, the running-in period was completed by a sliding distance of less than 700m, except for the load of 1.1N, where the running-in period of the composite was found to be prolonged to 1200m. Fig. 2 shows that the steady-state wear rate for both the monolithic alloy and the composite increased linearly with sliding distance. Using the principle of least squares, the wear rate, together with the standard error, was computed. The maximum standard error which resulted from the regular interruptions of the test was found to be $\pm 6\%$. This confirms the linear relationship between the steady-state wear rate and the sliding distance.

Fig. 2: Relationship between the steady-state volume loss and the sliding distance at two extreme loads, (a) 1.1N and (b) 48.3N.

Fig. 3 demonstrates the wear rate for both the monolithic alloy and the composite at three applied loads, as well as after different heat-treatments. The error bar indicates the variations from the mean value due to two duplicated tests. While the monolithic alloy and the

composite showed a marginal difference in wear rate at a load of 9.8N, wear rates for the monolithic alloy and the composite tested at the two extreme loads were clearly distinctive, regardless of the heat-treatment conditions. At the lowest load, the composite consistently showed a better wear performance than the monolithic alloy, whereas the opposite trend was found using the highest load. Compared with specimens in the as-extruded and the over-aged conditions, the peak-aged composite showed a marginal improvement in wear resistance at lower loads. Such a marginal improvement was not evident as the applied load increased to 48.3N. For the monolithic alloy, wear rates for the as-extruded and both the aged specimens were almost identical at loads of 1.1N and 9.8N. As the load increased to 48.3N, the as-extruded alloy showed the lowest wear rate followed by the peak-aged alloy, while the over-aged alloy demonstrated the highest wear rate.

Fig. 3: The influence of heat-treatment on the wear rate

Fig. 4: The friction behaviour of both the monolithic alloy and the composite

The coefficient of friction was calculated by dividing the recorded friction force by the normal applied load and was plotted against load, as in Fig. 4. Regardless of the heat-treatment conditions, the coefficient of friction generally decreased logarithmically with the load. At a load of 1.1N, the coefficient of friction of the composite was consistently higher than that of the monolithic alloy. However, no such trend was observed as the load increased to 9.8N and 48.3N.

DISCUSSION

SEM observations showed that the worn surface morphology of all the tested specimens shared the similar features, except for the composite when tested at a load of 1.1N. Fig. 5 shows the typical worn surface morphology of the composites tested at the two extreme loads. As reported in our earlier work [13], in which the influence of the applied load on the peak-aged materials was considered, the wear mechanism for the composites was found to be load dependent. At a load of 1.1N, the presence of the reinforcing Saffil limited the extent of direct contact between the matrix and the hard asperities of the mating disc surface, which in turn, prevented plastic deformation on the pin specimen extending from the contact surface to a greater depth. As a result, strain-hardened shear ripples associated with brittle cracks, were formed on the worn surface. Cyclic loading due to repeated sliding caused propagation of these brittle cracks and eventually the ripple delaminated giving loose debris. Fig. 5a and 5b

show a typical example of this mechanism, in which a small fraction of the shear ripples, indicated as 'R' in Fig. 5b, was about to delaminate to become flake-like debris, as it was surrounded by extensive cracks. When the load increased to 48.3N, the presence of the reinforcing Saffil becomes detrimental as the applied load was high enough to cause an increase in the area fraction of direct contact between the alloy matrix and disc asperities, Fig. 5c. Consequently, a greater depth of plastic deformation was induced, which further, caused fracture of the Saffil fibres beneath the worn surface, Fig. 5d. Such a fracture nucleated a void, as indicated at 'V', which inevitably favoured the delamination process.

Fig. 5: SEM micrographs of the composite tested at two extreme loads, (a) formation of shear ripples associated with brittle cracks on the worn surface, 1.1N, (b) high magnification of region 'A' in (a), (c) typical morphology of the worn surface, 48.3N, (d) subsurface deformation with fracture of the fibre, 48.3N

Despite of the higher hardness, the difference in the wear rate of the peak-aged monolithic alloy tested at loads of 1.1N and 9.8N, was found to be insignificant, compared with the as-extruded and the over-aged specimens. As the load increased to 48.3N, the as-extruded alloy, which has the lowest hardness, surprisingly showed the best wear resistance. These results obviously contradicted the Archard prediction [14], in which wear rate is found to be

inversely proportional to the hardness. As shown in our earlier study [13], a layer of compacted debris, which consisted mainly of Al and Fe, was formed on the contact surface of the pin specimen. In an Al-Si based MMC, a similar layer was also found by Venkataraman and Sundararajan [15], and the microhardness of this particular layer was reported to be higher than the bulk hardness by a factor of six. Based on this observation, the use of Archard's equation in predicting the dry sliding wear behaviour became complicated. However, neither bulk hardness nor surface layer hardness was suggested here, but rather, to point out that the use of Archard's equation in predicting wear behaviour was not appropriate in the wear system for which delamination was a dominant mechanism. For example, Saka, Pamies-Teixeira and Suh [16] found that although the increased hardness decreased the deformation rate, the loss of coherency at the matrix-particle interface with increasing hardness favoured crack nucleation, which eventually increased the rate of the delamination process. Although the presence of the fine precipitates in this case possibly limits the degree of plastic deformation, at the same time, at a load of 48.3N, they result in severe localised cracking due to extensive plastic strain. Therefore, this suggests that the absence of the fine precipitates formed during the ageing treatment, may be the reason for the best wear resistance which was found in the as-extruded alloy tested at a load of 48.3N.

By incorporating the Saffil fibres into the alloy matrix, the influence of the incoherent precipitates was over taken by the presence of the Saffil fibres. As mentioned earlier, when tested at a load of 48.3N, an extensive plastic deformation of the matrix caused fracture of the Saffil fibres at a depth of approximately 50 μ m beneath the worn surface. The fractured fibre nucleated a void, as indicated at 'V' in Fig. 5d, which has the potential to propagate and may link-up with the neighbouring voids to favour a delamination process, as the crack approaches the worn surface. By increasing flow stress of the alloy matrix, it was possible to reduce the extent of plastic deformation, which in turn, prevented or minimised fracture of the fibres. According to Alpas, Hu and Zhang [17], the flow stress is proportional to the hardness of the material. Thus, it is considered that the improvement in flow stress may lead to a better wear resistance in the peak-aged composite, when tested at higher loads, compared to the as-extruded and the over-aged composites. However, such an improvement was not capable of reducing the tendency for the fracture of Saffil as the applied load increased to 48.3N. This in turn lead to an insignificant difference in the wear performance of the composites at all heat-treatment conditions.

It was surprising to note that when tested at a load of 1.1N, the wear rate of the over-aged composite was higher than that of the as-extruded composite, which in turn showed a similar wear rate to that of the peak-aged composite, despite the fact that both the as-extruded and the over-aged composites have almost the same hardness. Several studies have revealed that a greater extent of ceramic pull-out was observed for the peak-aged specimen compared to the over-aged specimen [6-8]. For example, Pan and Cheng [6] attributed this observation to the change of the fracture path from the matrix/SiC interface in the peak-aged specimen to the alloy grain boundary in the case of the over-aged. By contrast, embrittlement of the reinforcement-matrix interface through increased S'/S precipitation in the vicinity of the reinforcement, decreased the wear resistance of 2009-SiCp composite as observed by Sannino and Rack [18]. By examining the over-aged specimen foil using transmission electron microscope (TEM), tilted to various angles, no evidence of second phase precipitates or a reaction layer was observed at the Saffil/matrix interface, Fig. 6. This suggests that a good bond between the Saffil fibres and the matrix was established, and difference in the extent of Saffil pull-out due to different heat-treatment conditions was unlikely in this study. Furthermore, in the present study, it was only in specimens tested at a load of 1.1N that some

broken Saffil fibres ($\sim 5\mu\text{m}$ in length), indicated as 'S' in Fig. 7, were revealed on the worn surface. For the case of higher loads, no evidence of Saffil fibres was observed on the worn surface and it is believed that the broken fibres were crushed and mixed together with the compacted debris and formed the mixed surface layer [13]. Even though the broken fibres were observed on the composites tested at a load of 1.1N, the number of broken fibres was too small for the dominant wear mechanism to be considered as fibre pull-out, compared to the observed greater extent of shear ripples associated with cracks. Compared to the as-extruded and the peak-aged composites, fewer shear ripples were observed on the worn surface of the over-aged composite. Based on the previous study [13], the formation of shear ripples was found to be increased in proportion to the volume fraction of Saffil fibres, while the wear rate showed the opposite trend. Although the mechanism of formation of shear ripples is not clearly understood at this stage, the presence of fewer of these features in the 10vol.% Saffil reinforced-composite, which was found in the previous study, resulted in an increase in the wear rate by more than twice that of the 20vol.% Saffil-reinforced composite. This suggests that the wear rate for the composite was sensitively dependent on the volume fraction of the reinforcement. Thus, the inferiority of the wear resistance of the over-aged composite, in this case, may be due to an inhomogeneous distribution of the Saffil fibres, which lead to variations in the volume fraction of Saffil at the contact surface. However, it was not possible to quantify the volume fraction (or area fraction) of the Saffil on the worn surface by using SEM, as most of the Saffil was smeared by the alloy matrix which had been plastically deformed.

Fig. 6: Transmission electron microscopy of the over-aged composite.

Fig. 7: SEM micrograph of broken Saffil fibres on the worn surface of the as-extruded composite, 1.1N.

CONCLUSIONS

The influence of heat-treatment on the dry sliding wear behaviour of a PM route elemental alloy AA6061 and a 20 vol.% Saffil-reinforced composite was investigated, under three different applied loads. On the basis of this study, the following conclusions were reached:

1. The steady-state wear rate for both the alloy and the composite was found to be linearly proportional to the sliding distance, regardless of the heat-treatment conditions.
2. At loads of 1.1N and 9.8N, similar wear rates were found for the monolithic alloy, but as the load increased to 48.3N, the as-extruded alloy showed the best wear resistance.
3. While the composite consistently showed a better wear resistance than the monolithic alloy at a load of 1.1N, the opposite trend was found at a load of 48.3N.

4. Compared to the as-extruded and the over-aged conditions, the increased in flow stress of the peak-aged composite lead to a better wear resistance at a load of 9.8N, where the tendency for the fracture of Saffil was considered to be reduced.
5. Little evidence for pull-out of Saffil fibres was observed in this work, regardless of the heat treatment conditions. Transmission electron microscopy revealed a clean Saffil/matrix interface with no evidence of a reaction layer.
6. The coefficient of friction generally decreased logarithmically with load, and was higher in the composite than the monolithic alloy, when tested under a load of 1.1N.

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